

Anion-exchange Extraction of Yttrium(III) and Neodymium(III) from Succinate Solution

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Selective separation of Nd^{III} and Y^{III} from La^{III} , Th^{IV} , U^{VI} , Dy^{III} and Sc^{III} is achieved by extraction from sodium succinate solution using Aliquat 336 as an extractant. The probable extracted species is $[R_2N^+M(C_4H_4O_2)_2]$. The results of separation of various synthetic mixtures are reported.

YTTRIUM promises to have an interesting future in the field of nuclear technology due to the low cross-section for neutron capture and high temperature stability. It is used as an additive to some of the refractory metals and alloys where its ability to form adherent oxide coatings on high temperature alloys has been demonstrated. Neodymium salt finds application in ceramic industry for colouring glasses and as glazer. The element is useful in the manufacture of lasers also. In view of these applications, separation and purification of both yttrium and neodymium is desired and solvent extraction fulfils this demand. Solvent extraction methods for yttrium(III) and neodymium(III) are very few and these have been critically reviewed by different authors¹⁻³. Most of the available methods deal with the extraction of radioisotopes, and systematic separation of yttrium(III) and neodymium(III) from commonly associated elements is lacking. The proposed method describes selective extraction and separation of both yttrium(III) or neodymium(III) from the associated metal ions such as lanthanum(III), scandium(III), dysprosium(III), cerium(IV), uranium(VI) and thorium(IV). The method is used successfully for the analysis of binary as well as multicomponent synthetic mixtures.

Experimental

A Zeiss spectrophotometer (Jena) with 1 cm silica cells and a Philips precision pH meter were used for absorbance and pH measurements, respectively.

The stock solutions of yttrium(III) and neodymium(III) were prepared by dissolving yttrium nitrate (1.65 g) in nitric acid and neodymium oxide (99.9% Nd_2O_3) (1.75 g) in perchloric acid solution and diluting to 100 ml with distilled water. The stock solutions were standardised and diluted as required ($50 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) for working solution.

Extracting solution: A 5% (w/v) solution of aliquat 336 (tricapryl methyl ammonium salt;

Kochlight) in benzene, equilibrated for 30 min with equal volumes of 2 M sodium succinate solution was used for extracting purposes. A 0.1% aqueous solution of arsenazo I was used for spectrophotometric determination of yttrium(III) and 0.05% aqueous solution of 4-(2-pyridylazo) resorcinol was used for spectrophotometric determination of neodymium(III). All other chemicals used in the work were of guaranteed grade.

Procedure: An aliquot of solution containing 25–75 μg of either yttrium(III) or neodymium(III) was mixed with enough sodium succinate solution (0.005–0.05 M for Y, or 0.01–0.2 M for Nd) in a total volume of 20 ml. pH of the solution was adjusted to 10–11 (by dilute NaOH and HNO_3 in case of Y) and 7–8 (by dilute NaOH and $HClO_4$ in case of neodymium). The solution was transferred into a 100 ml separatory funnel and equilibrate for 5 min with 5% aliquat 336 (5 ml) dissolved in benzene. The two layers, were separated, the aqueous phase discarded, and from the organic phase the metal ions (Y or Nd) were back-extracted with 0.1 M perchloric acid solution (2×5 ml). The combined aqueous phase was equilibrated with benzene (5 ml) to remove traces of dissolved amine and used for metal estimation as follows. For yttrium(III) estimation, 0.1% arsenazo I solution (1 ml) was added, the pH adjusted to 6 with dilute nitric acid and sodium hydroxide solution, diluted to 25 ml with water and the absorbance measured at 560 nm against the reagent blank⁴. Similarly, for neodymium(III) estimation, add 1 ml of 0.05% PAR solution (1 ml) was added, pH adjusted to 6.2 with dilute perchloric acid and sodium hydroxide solution, diluted to 25 ml with water and after 30 min the absorbance was measured at 515 nm against the reagent blank⁴.

Results and Discussion

Extraction conditions: The extraction of yttrium(III) and neodymium(III) was investigated at varying pH (4–13 for Y and 2–9 for Nd)

and succinate concentrations (0.005–0.05 M for Y and 0.01–0.2 M for Nd), (Figs. 1 and 2). The optimum pH for quantitative extraction of yttrium and neodymium were 10.5–11.5 and 7–8, respectively.

Fig. 1. Extraction of Y^{III} as a function of (—) pH and (---) sodium succinate concentration with 5% aliquat in benzene.

Fig. 2. Extraction of Nd^{III} as a function of (—) pH and (---) sodium succinate concentration with 5% aliquat in benzene.

Similarly, the sodium succinate concentrations should be 0.025 M for Y and 0.09–0.12 M for Nd. The percentage extraction (% E) and distribution ratios for yttrium(III) and neodymium(III) were calculated after stripping the metal ions from organic phase and subsequent spectrophotometric determination with arsenazo I and PAR, respectively. Variation in aliquat concentration showed that 5% solution of aliquat in benzene was needed for quantitative extraction of yttrium

and neodymium. The plot of log of distribution ratio vs log of aliquat concentration at fixed sodium succinate concentration (0.025 M for Y and 0.1 M for Nd) gave a slope of 1.3 for both Y^{III} and Nd^{III} . This shows that metal to amine ratio in the extracted species is probably 1:1. Similarly, log-log plot of distribution ratio vs sodium succinate at fixed pH and aliquat concentration gave a slope of nearly 2 for both Y^{III} and Nd^{III} indicating that metal to succinate ratio in the extracted species is 1:2. The probable extracted species is $[R_4N^+M(C_4H_4O_2)^-]$, where M stands for either Y^{III} or Nd^{III} and R_4N^+ for aliquat.

An interference study showed that for extraction and estimation of 50 μg of Y^{III} , 1000 μg each of Pr^{III} , phosphate and nitrate; 500 μg each of La^{III} , Th^{IV} , Nd^{III} , Ce^{IV} , Mo^{VI} , U^{VI} , Cu^{II} , Os^{VIII} and fluoride; 250 μg each of Sm^{III} , Ti^{IV} , Cr^{VI} , Pd^{II} and Ru^{III} ; 100 μg each of Gd^{III} , Dy^{III} , Zn and Ni do not show interference by the recommended procedure. However, ions such as Sc, Fe^{III} , citrate, tartarate and EDTA interfere severely. Similarly, in the extraction and determination of 50 μg of Nd^{III} , 1000 μg each of Sm^{III} , Gd^{III} , Y^{III} , Pr^{III} , Ce^{IV} , Pt^{IV} , I_2^{III} , citrate, tartarate, oxalate, thiourea and ascorbate; 500 μg each of La^{III} , Mo^{VI} , Sc^{III} , Th^{IV} , Co, Cd, nitrate, chloride and fluoride; 300 μg of Ti^{IV} ; 200 μg each of Zn and U^{VI} ; and 100 μg each of Ni, Dy^{III} , Ta^V and Rh^{III} do not interfere. However, ions such as Fe^{III} , nitrate and EDTA interfere severely and must be absent.

Separation of yttrium(III) or neodymium(III) from lanthanum(III): The quantitative extraction of yttrium or neodymium into aliquat (5% in benzene) from 0.025 M sodium succinate (pH 11) or 0.1 M sodium succinate (pH 7) facilitates their separation from La^{III} as it does not extract into amine and remains quantitatively in the aqueous phase where it is estimated photometrically with arsenazo-I⁶. Yttrium or neodymium are back-stripped and determined as described in the recommended procedure. The recoveries of all were $\geq 99.0\%$ for mixtures of 50 μg of Y^{III} or Nd^{III} with $< 500 \mu\text{g}$ of La^{III} .

Separation of yttrium(III) or neodymium(III) from uranium(VI) and dysprosium(III): Both U^{VI} and Dy^{III} show coextraction (20% U and 15% Dy) with Y^{III} or Nd^{III} . Their separation is however performed by selective scrubbing of uranium and dysprosium with water which do not strip either Y^{III} or Nd^{III} . The stripped solution is combined with the original aqueous extract containing unextracted U and Dy and in the combined extract these elements are determined photometrically with PAR⁷. Y^{III} or Nd^{III} are subsequently stripped and determined as described in the recommended procedure. The recoveries of all were $\geq 99.0\%$ for mixtures of 50 μg of Y^{III} or Nd^{III} with 100 μg of Dy and $< 500 \mu\text{g}$ of U^{VI} ,

Separation of yttrium(III) or neodymium(III) from thorium(IV) and cerium(IV): Quadrivalent Th and Ce also coextract along with Y^{III} or Nd^{III} . Their separation is however performed by selective stripping technique. From the organic phase containing Th and Y^{III} or Nd^{III} and Th is first stripped with 0.1 M HNO_3 solution (2×5 ml) and determined in the aqueous phase titrimetrically⁸. Nitric acid does not cause stripping of either yttrium or neodymium. They are subsequently stripped and determined by the recommended procedure. Similarly, from the organic phase containing Ce^{IV} , Y^{III} or Nd^{III} , Ce^{IV} is first stripped with 6 M H_2SO_4 (2×5 ml) and determined in the aqueous phase titrimetrically⁹. Sulphuric acid does not back-extract Y or Nd. They are removed from the organic phase and subsequently determined as described in the general procedure. The recoveries of all were $\geq 99.0\%$ for mixtures of 50 μg of Y^{III} or Nd^{III} with $< 1000 \mu g$ of both Th^{IV} and Ce^{IV} .

Separation of neodymium(III) from scandium(III): Sc^{III} coextract with Nd^{III} (from 0.1 M sodium succinate solution adjusted to pH 7.5) into 5% aliquot solution in benzene. Scandium is stripped selectively with 1 M HCl solution (10 ml) and determined in the aqueous phase photometrically with arsenazo I¹⁰. Nd^{III} is finally stripped and determined as given in the general procedure. The recoveries of Sc^{III} and Nd^{III} is $\geq 99.0\%$.

Separation of Sc^{III} and Y^{III} is however not feasible by the proposed method. Similarly, mutual separation of Y^{III} and Nd^{III} is also not feasible.

The proposed method permits the extraction and determination of yttrium (50 μg) from multi-component mixtures containing ions (in μg) such as Ag (100), Au (100), Pd (250), Pt (200) and Cu (200) or Gd (100), Dy (100) and La (250). Similarly extraction and determination of neodymium (50 μg) is possible in presence of ions (in μg) such as Pd (200), Pt (500), Ag (100) and Au (250) or Dy (100), La (250) and Y (200).

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